

Evaluation of the National Education Policy 2020 with the Aim of Reaching the Goal of Sustainable Development

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Abstract:- Achieving a high standard of education is essential for every nation's development, and education policy is one strategy for doing so. A major overhaul of India's educational system is being sought after by the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 programme. Everyone should have access to high-quality education, which will position India as a global leader in terms of economic development, social fairness and equality, scientific advancement, national fusion, and cultural preservation (NEP 2020).

NEP 2020 has introduced on 29 July 2020 it replaced the NEP 1986. The Mahamana's vision and vision of NEP is in line with the fourth goal of the United Nation Sustainable Development goals which ensures equitable and quality education and promote lifelong opportunity for all. Though NEP 2020 has impacted both school education and higher education equally, this paper focuses on the fourth sustainable development goal.

This paper's major emphasis is on the present tactics used in India's education system for contextualising SDG 4 and including NEP 2020. The fourth SDG's performance in India is also examined, as is the trend of higher education in India.

Keywords:- National Education Policy (NEP), Sustainable Development Goal, Quality Education, Equity, Access, Inclusion.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is a key to success of any country it plays central role in developing countries as a whole. Education is the essence of human development. Government of India has finalized the New Education Policy 2020 with regards to present requirement of the country. The main aim of NEP 2020 is to make India a knowledge hub as it was earlier in ancient time, but equipped with skill and technological upgradation with ICT, Research and Innovation. India has achieved significant targets of fourth sustainable development goal, it ensures equitable and quality education with lifelong learning opportunity for all. India has also made progress towards goal Education for all. Through the

constitution and government various policies and programs have been introduced for providing Fundamental right of education, free and compulsory education to all children within the age group of six to fourteen, various initiatives have been taken that have given much required encouragement to education system in India. Through these initiatives enrolment ratio has been improved in education but quality concern has remained to be address now it's time to drag emphasis from quantity to quality (Pandey, n.d.) . Sustainable development goals are comprehensive and inclusive which includes all discipline of knowledge. SDGs are viewed as the extension of Millennium development goals and based on mainly three dimension; economic, social and environmental. Sustainable Development Goals are adopted in 2015, it has 17 goals and 169 targets related to issues which required urgent attention at present and also in near future. Sustainable Development Goals are also called as 2030 agenda. A well-organise education policy is necessary for every country because education is the foundation for any success. Recently in 2020, India's New National Education Policy has been introduced by the Government of India it was passed by legislative assembly and framed by Dr. K. Kasturiranjana committee. New Education Policy is also based on SDG's fourth goal that ensures quality education for all. For eliminating the gap between current status of education in India and 4th SDG's target there was need to change education system and introduce new education policy that should be aligned with fourth SDG because SDG targets are the requirement at global level. Therefore, New education policy come into the picture it will boost the education system towards achieving the objectives of fourth sustainable development goals. Introduction of NEP is the first step towards new education system the objectives the new education policy will be achieved only when it will be implemented as expected. Policies success only when implementation done as expected.

➤ Vision of Mahamana and NEP 2020 Towards Equity and Inclusion:

Pandit Madan Mohan Malaviya was an Indian scholar and educational reformer. Malaviya endeavoured to promote modern education in India and with the dream of modern education in India he has founded the great university Banaras Hindu University in 1916, called as capital of

knowledge. Mahamana’s vision was to provide modern education with quality and there should be equality and inclusivity, no one should be left behind because of one’s caste, birthplace, community, etc. NEP 2020 aims that the education system should contribute to an equitable and vibrant knowledge society, by providing high-quality education to all. It has built its pillars on the foundation stone of 4th SDG which emphasises on inclusive, equitable and quality education with equal opportunity of lifelong learning for all.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

➤ *The objectives of the study are as follow:*

- To increase awareness about the education trend in India.
- To develop an understanding of the 4th SDG and NEP’s contribution towards achieving the 4th sustainable development goal.
- To discuss the performance of India in achieving targets of the 4th SDG and also show the performance of India in education, Gender, and Inequality at the global level.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This paper is descriptive in nature. This paper is based on secondary data and collected from various sources such as articles, research papers, websites, published reports by the Government, and other published sources.

➤ *Tracking Progress of Education in India:*

Through these data, the paper is showing the trend of education in India in both school and higher education.

➤ *School Education*

Although India has made significant progress in school education as well as in higher education. The Gross Enrolment Ratio in Primary education increased from 101.3 percent 2018-2019 to 103.39 percent in 2021-2022, in Upper Primary and Upper Secondary education GER increased from 87.7 and 50.1 percent in 2018-2019 to 94.67 and 57.56 percent in 2021-2022 respectively. In secondary education GER has decline from 79.8 percent in 2020-2021 to 79.56 percent in 2021-2022 (Table 1).

Table 1 Gross Enrolment Raio (GER) in School Education- All Catogries of Students

Years	Primary (1-5)	Upper Primary (6-8)	Secondary (9-10)	Upper Secondary (11-12)
2018-2019	101.3	87.7	76.9	50.1
2019-2020	102.7	89.7	77.9	51.4
2020-2021	103.3	92.2	79.8	53.8
2021-2022	103.39	94.67	79.56	57.56

Fig 1 Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER) - All Categories of Student

Total School Enrolment also has an increasing trend but it also declines after 2020-2021 that time whole country was suffering with Pandemic. Upper Primary Enrolment increased from 6.4 crores in 2018-2019 to 6.68 crore in 2021-2022. In Higher Secondary enrolment increased from 2.6 cr. in 2018-2019 to 2.86 cr. in 2021-2022. But Pre-Primary, Primary and Secondary education enrolment declined from 1.06 cr. to 12.2 cr. and 3.9 cr. in 2020-2021 to 0.95 cr., 12.18 cr. and 3.85 cr. in 2021-2022 respectively (Table 2).

Table 2 Total Enrolment in School Education (in Crore)

Years	Pre-Primary	Primary	Upper Primary	Secondary	Higher Secondary
2018-2019	1.2	12	6.4	3.8	2.6
2019-2020	1.4	12.2	6.5	3.8	2.6
2020-2021	1.06	12.2	6.6	3.9	2.7
2021-2022	0.95	12.18	6.68	3.85	2.86

School Dropout rate have decline in Primary education from 4.5 in 2018-2019 to 0.8 in 2020-2021 but next year the rate has increased from 0.8 in 2020-2021 to 1.45 in 2021-2022. In Upper Primary rate has decline from 4.7 in 2018-2019 to 1.9 in 2020-2021 but next year it has also increased from 1.9 in 2020-2021 to 3.02. In Secondary education rate has decline from 17.9 in 2018-2019 to 14.6 in 2020-2021 but it has also increased from 14.6 in 2020-2021 to 12.61 (Table 3).

Table 3 Drop Out Rate in School Education

Years	Primary	Upper Primary	Secondary
2018-2019	4.5	4.7	17.9
2019-2020	1.5	2.6	16.1
2020-2021	0.8	1.9	14.6
2021-2022	1.45	3.02	12.61

Fig 2 School Enrollment (in Crore)

Fig 3 Drop out Rate

Gender Parity Index is also improving in all categories of school education but from 2020-2021 it declines. In upper primary GPI has decline from 1.02 in 2019-2020 to 1 in 2021-2022. In secondary GPI has decline from 1.00 in 2019-2020 to 0.99 in 2020-2021 and then increase to 1 in 2021-2022. In higher secondary GPI has increase in 2019-2020 then decline from 1.04 in 2019-2020 to 1.02 in 2021-2022. (Table 4).

Table 4 Gender Parity Index (GPI) at GER - All Categories

Years	Primary (1-5)	Upper Primary (6-8)	Secondary (9-10)	Higher Secondary (11-12)
2018-2019	1.01	1.02	1.00	1.03
2019-2020	1.02	1.02	1.00	1.04
2020-2021	1.02	1.01	0.99	1.03
2021-2022	1.03	1.00	1.00	1.02

Fig 4 Gender Parity Index (GPI) at GER - All Categories

➤ Data Source for School Education:

- (Udise_201920, n.d.)
- (Report on UNIFIED DISTRICT INFORMATION SYSTEM FOR EDUCATION PLUS (UDISE+), n.d.)
- (Report on UNIFIED DISTRICT INFORMATION SYSTEM FOR EDUCATION PLUS (UDISE+), 2018)
- (UNIFIED DISTRICT INFORMATION SYSTEM FOR EDUCATION, n.d.)

➤ Higher Education

Although India has also made significant progress towards education attainment in Higher education. The Gross Enrolment Ratio in higher education has increased from 12.30 in 2006-2007 to 27.01 in 2019-2020, chart is also showing increasing trend (Table 5).

Table 5 Gross Enrollment Ratio in Higher Education (18-23 Years)

Years	Gross Enrollment Ratio
2006-2007	12.39
2007-2008	13.1
2008-2009	13.7
2009-2010	15
2010-2011	19.4
2011-2012	20.8
2012-2013	21.5
2013-2014	23
2014-2015	24.3
2015-2016	24.5
2016-2017	25.2

2017-2018	25.8
2018-2019	26.3
2019-2020	27.1

Total enrolment in higher education has also increasing trend, it has increased from 15552519 in 2006-2007 to 38536359 with this population is also increasing (Table 6). Gross Enrollment Ratio

Table 6 Total Enrolment in Higher Education

Year	Total Enrolment in Higher Education
2006-2007	15552519
2007-2008	17211216
2008-2009	18500325
2009-2010	20740740
2010-2011	27499749
2011-2012	29184331
2012-2013	30152417
2013-2014	32336234
2014-2015	34211637
2015-2016	34584781
2016-2017	35705905
2017-2018	36642378
2018-2019	37399388
2019-2020	38536359

The Gender parity index in Higher education is also improving, it tends to more than 1. It has increased from 0.69 in 2006-2007 to 1.01 in 2019-2020 (Table 7). GPI indicates parity between males and females. If GPI is less than 1 it means females are more disadvantaged towards education than males.

Fig 5 Gros Enrolment Ratio

Fig 6 Total Enrolment in Higher Education

Fig 7 Gender Parity Index

Table 7 Gender Parity Index in Higher Education (18-23 Years)

Years	Gender Parity Index
2006-2007	0.69
2007-2008	0.70
2008-2009	0.72
2009-2010	0.74
2010-2011	0.86
2011-2012	0.88
2012-2013	0.89
2013-2014	0.92
2014-2015	0.92
2015-2016	0.92
2016-2017	0.94
2017-2018	0.97
2018-2019	1.00
2019-2020	1.01

As the data tables and charts demonstrate, both the gender parity index and education enrolment have been rising. However, after 2020, there has been a little fall, primarily because of the COVID-19 epidemic, which was also the cause of the global education crisis. After 2020, the rate of educational dropout is also rising. The majority of education systems have been severely impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic, and in an effort to get back on the correct track with education, our nation has recently unveiled the 2020 Education Policy.

➤ Data Source for Higher Education:

- (ALL INDIA SURVEY ON HIGHER EDUCATION GOVERNMENT OF INDIA MINISTRY OF HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT DEPARTMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATION NEW DELHI 2013, n.d.)
- (ALL INDIA SURVEY ON HIGHER EDUCATION GOVERNMENT OF INDIA MINISTRY OF HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT DEPARTMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATION NEW DELHI 2014, n.d.)
- (AISHE2013-14, n.d.)
- (All INDIA SURVEY ON HIGHER EDUCATION) GOVERNMENT OF INDIA MINISTRY OF HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT DEPARTMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATION NEW DELHI 2015, 2012)
- (AISHE2014-15, n.d.)
- (AISHE2017-18, n.d.)
- (All India Survey on Higher Education GOVERNMENT OF INDIA MINISTRY OF HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT DEPARTMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATION NEW DELHI 2017, 2016)
- (Key Results of the AISHE 2015-16, n.d.)
- (StatHTE_2008-09, n.d.)
- (AISHE Final Report 2018-19, n.d.)
- (Goel, 2011)
- (INDEX, n.d.)
- (Central State, n.d.)

➤ Sustainable Development Goals

The Sustainable Development Goals are the global goals which includes 17 targets designed on the basis of required need of the world at present and in near future. The SDGs are introduced by United Nation General Assembly in 2015 that intended to be achieved by 2030. They are also called as 2030 Agenda. Through SDGs United Nation has connected social, economic and environment aspects with sustainability. This includes 17 goals but this paper emphasis on fourth sustainable development goal: that ensures inclusive, equitable and quality education for all.

Fourth goal of SDGs are linked with other SDGs and we can say that all SDGs are interrelated with each other, all are important for Sustainable Development. Goal 4 that ensures inclusive, equitable and quality education with equal opportunity of lifelong learning for all.

➤ *Goal 4 has Various Targets that Intended to be Achieved in Near Future:*

- Make sure that, by 2030, all boys and girls receive a primary and secondary education that is equal, free, and of high quality and produces learning outcomes that are both pertinent and useful.
- Make sure that, by 2030, all boys and girls have access to high-quality pre-primary education, care, and early childhood development by 2030 so they are prepared for primary school.
- Make ensuring that all women and men have equal access to high-quality, reasonably priced technical, vocational, and tertiary education by 2030, including university education.
- Increase the proportion of young people and adults with the necessary skills—technical and vocational—for employment, good jobs, and entrepreneurship by a significant margin by 2030.
- Eliminate gender gaps in education by 2030, and make sure that those who are most in need—people with disabilities, children in danger, and indigenous peoples—have equitable access to all educational and career opportunities.
- Make sure that by 2030, every young person and a significant percentage of adults—men and women alike—are literate and numerate.
- By 2030, make sure that all students have the knowledge and abilities necessary to support sustainable development, including those of others. This can be achieved through promoting gender equality, human rights, sustainable lifestyles, a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship, and an appreciation of cultural diversity and the role that culture plays in sustainable development.
- Construct and renovate educational buildings that include the needs of children, people with disabilities, and women in order to create inclusive, safe, and productive learning spaces for all.
- Increase the number of scholarships available to developing nations, especially the least developed nations, small island developing states, and African nations, by a significant margin by 2020. These scholarships can be used for postsecondary education, technical, engineering, scientific, and vocational programmes in developed and developing nations alike, as well as for vocational training and information and communications technology.
- Increase the number of trained teachers available by 2030, notably through international collaboration for

teacher preparation in developing nations—particularly small island developing states and the least developed nations.

- *Data Source : (SDG INDIA Index & Dashboard 2020-21 Partnerships in the Decade of Action, n.d.)*

➤ *Performance of India Towards Indicators of 4th SDG:*

- Adjusted Net Enrolment Ratio in elementary education (class 1-8):
- India has achieved 87.26% target in the Adjusted Net Enrolment Ratio at Elementary Education while the Target is 100 percent.
- Average annual dropout rate:
- The average annual dropout rate in India is 17.87 percent at the secondary level while the Target is 8.8 percent.
- Gross Enrolment Ratio in higher secondary:
- The Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in India is 50.14 percent at higher secondary level while the Target is 100 percent.
- Student's minimum proficiency in grade 8:
- In India 71.9 percent of students in class 8 has achieved at least a minimum proficiency level in Language and Mathematics in terms of nationally defined learning outcomes at the end of class 8 while the target is 100 percent.
- Enrolment Ratio in higher education:
- In India only 26.3 percent of students in the age group of 18-23 years were enrolled in higher education while the target in SDG is 50 percent, also in NEP 2020 by 2035.
- Education level among Persons with Disability:
- India has 19.3 percent of persons with disability (15 years and above) who have completed at least secondary education while the target is 100 percent.
- Gender Parity in higher education:
- All India GPI value is 1 that implies a parity between females and males (18-23 years) in higher education in the country.
- Literacy levels:
- The literacy level among persons in India within the age group 15 years and above stood at 74.6 percent while the target is 100 percent.
- Infrastructure in schools:
- In India 84.76 percent of schools had access to basic infrastructure (electricity and drinking water) while the target is 100 percent.
- Proportion of trained teachers:
- In India 82.62 percent of teachers are trained at secondary level while the target is 100 percent.
- Pupil-teacher ratio:
- The all-India pupil teacher ratio stands at 21 at secondary level while the target is at least 30 percent.

(SDG INDIA Index & Dashboard 2020-21 Partnerships in the Decade of Action, n.d.)

Table 8 Performance of India Towards Achieving 4th Sustainable Development Goal

TARGET	INDIA (2020-2021)	SDG INDICATORS	
100	87.26	Adjusted Net Enrolment Ratio in Elementary (class1-8) education	4.1
8.8	17.87	Average annual dropout rate in secondary education (class 9-10)	4.1
100	50.14	Gross Enrolment ratio in Higher secondary education (class 11-12)	4.1
100	71.9	Percentage of students in grade VIII achieving at least minimum proficiency level as per nationally defined learning outcomes to be attained by students at the end of that above grade	4.1
50	26.3	Gross Enrolment Ratio in Higher education (age group 18-23 years)	4.3
1	1	Gender Parity Index in Higher education (age group 18-23 years)	4.5
100	19.3	Percentage of persons with disability who have completed at least secondary education (age group 15 years and above)	4.5
100	74.6	Percentage of persons who are literate (15 years and above)	4.6
100	84.76	Percentage of schools with access to basic infrastructure (electricity, drinking water)	4.a
100	82.62	Percentage of trained teachers at secondary level (class 9-10)	4.c
30	21	Pupil Teacher Ratio (PTR) at secondary level (class 9-10)	4.c

Data Source: (SDG INDIA Index & Dashboard 2020-21 Partnerships in the Decade of Action, n.d.)

➤ *India’s Performance at Global Level*

According to Sustainable Development Goal report 2022, It is the assessment report of world’s progress towards achieving its sustainable development goal, in 4th SDG India was in the state of stagnating. India has achieved 121 rank out of 163 countries with 60.3 score in the global Sustainable Development Goal. In 2020 India was on 117 rank but in 2021 India was on 120th rank. India slipped three spot. Table 9 is showing the performance of G20 countries towards education, gender and inequality in that India is the

lowest year of free education, 8 years and compulsory education 8 years and achieved lowest score in commitment to reduce inequality 0.45 score but in gender equality score by world bank showing that Indonesia with score 64.4 and Russian federation with score 73.1 are behind India with score 74.4. The India’s Expenditure on research and development, percentage of GDP was more than three G20 countries but less than fifteen G20 countries that is 0.7 (Table:9).

Table 9 Education, Gender and Inequality

G20 Countries	Years of free education in the Law (UNESCO, 2020)	Year of compulsory education in the law (UNESCO,2020)	Commitment to reduce inequalities: Tax Progressivity & Protection of Labour Right (score, 2020, Oxfam & DFI)	Gender Equality in the Law (score,2020, World Bank)	Expenditure on research and development (% of GDP, 2018,UNESCO)
Argentina	12	12	0.63	79.4	0.5
Australia	13	10	0.69	96.6	1.9
Brazil	12	12	0.57	85	1.2
China	9	9	0.54	75.6	2.1
Canada	12	10	0.74	100	1.5
France	12	10	0.72	100	2.2
Germany	13	13	0.75	97.5	3.1
India	8	8	0.45	74.4	0.7
Indonesia	12	9	0.54	64.4	0.2
Italy	8	12	0.67	97.5	1.4
Japan	9	9	0.69	78.8	3.3
Korea, Rep.	9	9	0.63	85	4.5
Mexico	12	12	0.56	88.8	0.3
Russian Federation	11	11	0.67	73.1	1

Saudi Arabia	12	9	No Data	80	0.8
South Africa	12	9	0.69	88.1	0.8
Turkey	12	12	0.56	82.5	1
United Kingdom	13	11	0.67	97.5	1.7
United States	12	12	0.66	91.3	2.8

Source: (Sachs et al., 2022) Sustainable Development Report 2022

Fig 8 Education, Gender and Inequality

➤ *Initiatives are Taken Under NEP 2020 that Relates to the Targets of 4th SDG:*

Goal 4 of SDGs ensures that inclusive and equitable education for all that aligned with this NEP 2020. NEP’s one of the visions is equity and inclusion as all educational decisions starts and ends with equity and inclusion. NEP

2020 will further help in improving India's progress towards achieving Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG4) of ensuring free, equitable, and quality education for all children. There is a table given below which shows the initiatives taken under NEP 2020 that relates to the targets of SDG 4.

Table 10 Initiatives are Taken Under NEP 2020 that Relates to the Targets of 4th SDG

SDG 4 Targets	NEP 2020
Make sure that, by 2030, all boys and girls receive a primary and secondary education that is equal, free, and of high quality and produces learning outcomes that are both pertinent and useful.	<p>Equality and inclusiveness are two of NEP's guiding principles, and policies support these goals in education. NEP seeks to ensure that no kid is denied the chance to learn and grow intellectually as a result of discrimination. Although there are still major gaps in education equity related to socioeconomic class and gender across all educational levels, the Indian education system and government policies have made great strides in this direction. The NEP 2020 aims to close these gaps and achieve inclusivity and equality in education across the nation. Several steps have been made to guarantee fairness, inclusivity, and quality for successful learning outcomes at all educational levels:</p> <p>A concerted effort will be made to monitor the essential issues and suggestions pertaining to early childhood education and care, enrollment, basic reading and numeracy, access, and attendance for socioeconomically disadvantaged groups, or SEDGs.</p> <p>Children from indigenous groups will have special procedures to ensure they receive high-quality education.</p> <p>Keeping an eye on how well children from SC, ST, and OBC groups are meeting their learning objectives in order to ensure that they are effective.</p> <p>Special Education Zones (SEZs) with large populations of economically disadvantaged groups will be established.</p> <p>On a greater scale, scholarships and fee waivers will be extended to deserving students from all SEDGs.</p>

	<p>To improve the mental health of students, hire counsellors for schools. More JNVs and KVS schools will be established in aspirational districts and SEZs. Establishing a fund for transgender and female students that promotes gender inclusion.</p>
<p>4.2 Make sure that, by 2030, all boys and girls have access to high-quality pre-primary education, care, and early childhood development by 2030 so they are prepared for primary school.</p>	<p>Numerous initiatives have been implemented to guarantee Universal Access and Quality Education to Early Childhood Care & Education (ECCE), preparing students for the next educational step. For instance, all children from three to six years old have free, secure, and excellent early childhood education at Anganwadis, Pre-school, and Balvatika. Two sections comprise the Foundational Learning Curriculum for children ages 3 to 8: (I) in ECCE from ages 3-6; (ii) in primary school classes I and II from ages 6 to 8. Every child under the age of five will go to a "Preparatory Class," also known as a "Balvatika," prior to class 1. Play-based, activity-based, inquiry-based, flexible learning with multiple facets. The multifaceted framework encompasses the following topics: play-based and discovery-based learning, self-identity, teamwork and collaboration, relationship with nature, logical thinking and problem solving, ethics, developing curiosity, etiquette, emotional and behavioural development, languages, numbers, counting, painting, visual art and crafts, colours, drawing, shapes, and indoor and outdoor play. All First Grade pupils will participate in a three-month play-based "school preparation module" designed by NCERT. NCERT will create the National Curricular and Pedagogical Framework for Early Childhood Education (NCPFCE), which will be in line with both national and international best practices and the most recent ECCE research. The Ministries of Education, Women and Child Development, Health and Family Welfare, and Tribal Affairs will collaborate to carry out the implementation.</p>
<p>4.3 Make ensuring that all women and men have equal access to high-quality, reasonably priced technical, vocational, and tertiary education by 2030, including university education. 4.4 Increase the proportion of young people and adults with the necessary skills—technical and vocational—for employment, good jobs, and entrepreneurship by a significant margin by 2030.</p>	<p>Several steps have been taken to ensure the integration of vocational education at all levels: All students will have access to this "LokVidya," or knowledge developed in India. A practice-based curriculum should be suitably created for Grades 6–8. A National Skills Qualifications Framework for each discipline of vocation or profession will be created for the Skills Framework. To develop a vocational craft, all sixth- through eighth-graders will work as interns with local vocational experts like potters, carpenters, gardeners, and artists. Analysis of the skill gap will be done in order to identify and map out local opportunities. Courses that will be made available via Open and Distance Learning (ODL). By the year 2025, a minimum of 50% of students must have had exposure to vocational education. A variety of disciplines, including the social sciences, arts, humanities, and languages, as well as professional, technical, and vocational subjects, should be included for transdisciplinary and comprehensive growth. Technical education encompasses degree and certificate degrees in fields vital to India's overall growth, such as engineering, technology, management, architecture, town planning, pharmacy, hotel management, and culinary technology. To help students at all levels develop these numerous crucial skills, additional initiatives will be implemented, such as the introduction of modern subjects like Artificial Intelligence, Design Thinking, Holistic Health, Organic Living, Environmental Education, Global Citizenship Education (GCED), etc. at pertinent stages.</p>
<p>4.5 Eliminate gender gaps in education by 2030, and make sure that those who are most in need—people with disabilities, children in danger, and indigenous peoples—have equitable access to all educational and career opportunities. 4.a Construct and renovate educational buildings that include the needs of children, people with disabilities, and women in order to create inclusive, safe, and productive learning spaces for all.</p>	<p>Regarding Assisting Children with Special Needs: Monitoring normal Schooling: From elementary school (classes 1–8) to higher education, children with special needs (CWSN) will be observed during the normal schooling process. Assistive Devices and Parent Orientation: Technology-enabled tools and devices for children with special needs, along with parent and carer orientation. Alternative Schools: To maintain their alternative teaching approaches, alternative school models will be supported. Sign language education modules: NIOS will create top-notch sign language education modules. Teacher Certificate Programmes: These programmes prepare pre-service and in-service teachers to become special educators. Facilitating Systems for High-Quality Education: Facilitating systems that allow Divyang or CWSN to obtain High-Quality Education.</p>

	<p>Actions to Promote Gender Parity, Particularly for Girls:</p> <p>Girls' Rights and Safety: Giving careful consideration to the rights and safety of all children, especially girls, in order to keep them in school and to strengthen education, KGBVs should be extended to grade 12.</p> <p>Offering everyone equal chances will be the main focus of Bridging the Gender Gap. A fund for gender inclusion for transgender and female students will be established.</p> <p>Girls will be the focus of policies and programmes, with an emphasis on creating measures that address female pupils that fall under the SEDGs.</p> <p>"Gender Sensitivity" should be taught as a core subject.</p> <p>Regarding the Assistance of Talented or Gifted Students:</p> <p>To improve students' abilities to compete in nationwide student Olympiads and contests in a variety of subjects, in which all students are eligible to compete.</p> <p>NCERT and NCTE will create guidelines for the education of brilliant youngsters.</p> <p>Widespread use of technology to inspire gifted and talented kids to use it to further their education and develop new skills.</p> <p>Encourage kids who are gifted or talented to pursue interests outside of the core curriculum.</p> <p>Project-based groups, which should be promoted and assisted in schools at all levels for students.</p> <p>Attempts to guarantee broad involvement in education through interventions in the rural sector and in regional languages.</p> <p>B.Ed. programmes that specialise on teaching gifted kids will be offered.</p>
<p>4.6 Make sure that by 2030, every young person and a significant percentage of adults—men and women alike—are literate and numerate.</p>	<p>Reaching the goal of foundational literacy and numeracy is necessary for improving the quality and achieving learning outcomes (FLN).</p> <p>By the third grade, the goal is to have achieved foundational literacy and numeracy. Foundational learning skills will be made available through universal acquisition.</p> <p>There will be a national mission on foundational literacy and numeracy. Early learning will focus on early reading, writing, and mathematics.</p> <p>There will be ample opportunities to upgrade one's knowledge of the most recent pedagogies pertaining to basic reading and numeracy.</p> <p>The recommendations and key issues pertaining to basic literacy and numeracy skills will be directed at groups that are socioeconomically disadvantaged.</p> <p>There will be five different programme types included in the adult education curriculum:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Basic Numeracy and Literacy Vital Life Skills Equipping Vocational Skills Foundational Knowledge Ongoing Education <p>The Digital Infrastructure for Knowledge Sharing will host a national repository of excellent resources on basic literacy and numeracy (DIKSHA).</p> <p>Basic literacy, numeracy, and other fundamental abilities would be assessed in the Grade 3 exam in order to track and improve the educational system over time.</p> <p>Basic literacy and numeracy instruction will be a part of every B.Ed. degree.</p>
<p>4.7 By 2030, make sure that all students have the knowledge and abilities necessary to support sustainable development, including those of others. This can be achieved through promoting gender equality, human rights, sustainable lifestyles, a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship, and an appreciation of cultural diversity and the role that culture plays in sustainable development.</p>	<p>Developing abilities, attitudes, and behaviours that support responsible commitment to sustainable development, human rights, and global well-being—qualities that genuinely reflect a global citizen—is one of NEP's visions.</p> <p>The curriculum will include environmental education as well, covering a number of topics like pollution, waste management, sanitation, climate change, biodiversity and biological diversity conservation, management of biological resources and biodiversity, conservation of forests and wildlife, and sustainable development and living.</p> <p>Value-based education is therefore crucial for our nation to maintain its culture and values. It will teach lessons in seva/service and community service, as well as righteous conduct (dharma), peace (shanti), and the development of humanistic, ethical, constitutional, and universal human values of truth (Satya), love (prem), scientific temper, citizenship values, nonviolence (ahimsa), life skills, and more. These lessons will be regarded as essential components of a holistic education.</p> <p>Environmental education will be emphasised in all B.Ed. programmes, with a focus on sustainable development and environmental awareness. This will ensure that the Indian Constitution's Fundamental Duties (Article 51A) and other provisions are followed when teaching and performing any activity that involves the environment.</p>

	<p>The nation's economic growth and the provision of sustainable livelihoods are further enhanced by higher education. An increasing number of young Indians are expected to pursue higher education as the country progresses towards being a knowledge hub for the economy and society.</p> <p>In addition to genomic studies, neuroscience, biotechnology, and nanotechnology, India needs to train professionals in a number of rapidly evolving fields, including artificial intelligence (AI), 3-D printing, big data analysis, and machine learning. These fields have significant implications for the environment, health, and sustainable living and will play a key role in improving youth employability.</p> <p>As a result of technological advancements, we must adapt both our way of life and the way we teach our children. This means that lessons on clean and renewable energy, water conservation, sustainable agriculture, environmental preservation, and other green initiatives must be given top priority in the classroom.</p>
<p>4.c Increase the number of trained teachers available by 2030, notably through international collaboration for teacher preparation in developing nations—particularly small island developing states and the least developed nations.</p>	<p>The following measures will be taken to improve teacher education: • Programmes will be offered at composite, multidisciplinary institutions.</p> <p>A new, extensive national curriculum framework for teacher education is in the works.</p> <p>To be admitted to the B.Ed. programme, NTA will provide an exam.</p> <p>The National Higher Education Regulatory Council (NHERC) will serve as the exclusive authority overseeing the higher education industry, which includes teacher preparation.</p> <p>A four-year integrated B.Ed. programme will also be available with merit-based scholarships.</p> <p>Establishing a nationwide mission to mentor teacher education, utilising a sizable pool of exceptional senior/retired faculty members.</p> <p>Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) operating independently that fall short of standards may face severe consequences.</p> <p>All phases will see the administration of Teacher Eligibility Tests (TETs), which are intended to improve teacher preparation.</p> <p>Only pedagogically sound, multidisciplinary, and integrated educational programmes will be offered.</p>

Data Source: (National Education Policy 2020 Ministry of Human Resource Development Government of India, n.d.-b) (SDG INDIA Index & Dashboard 2020-21 Partnerships in the Decade of Action, n.d.)

After seeing the comparative table (discussed above) of 4th SDG and NEP 2020 we can say that 4th SDG was the foundation stone for NEP 2020. NEP 2020 will lead India towards achieving the targets of 4th SDG.

➤ *Centrally Sponsored Initiatives for Achieving Indicators of 4th Sustainable Development Goals:*

1. Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, 2. National Programme of Mid-Day Meal in Schools (MDM) 3. Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan 4. National Means-cum-Merit Scholarship Scheme(NMMSS) 5. Strengthening of Teacher Training Institutions 6. Pandit Madan Mohan Malaviya National Mission on Teachers and Teaching (PMMMNTT) 7. National Scheme for Incentive to Girl Child for Secondary Education (NSIGSE) HRD (School Education & Literacy) 8. Pre-matric scholarships for SC, OBC and vulnerable groups 9. Pre-matric scholarships for children of those engaged in unclean occupations and prone to health hazards 10. Pre-matric Scholarship to students with disabilities 11. Other scholarships & fellowships for SC, OBC Students 12. Free coaching for SC students 13. Hostels for SC & OBC students 14. Pre-matric scholarships for minority students 15. National Child Labour Project (including grants-in-aid to voluntary agencies & reimbursement of assistance to bonded labour) Labour and Employment 16. Umbrella ICDS (Aganwadi Services) 17. Rashtriya Uchhatar Shiksha Abhiyan 18. Scholarship for College and University Students 19. Interest Subsidy and Contribution for

- Guarantee Funds 20. Technical Education Quality Improvement Programme (EAP) 21. Post-matric scholarships for SC, OBC and other vulnerable community students 22. Post-matric scholarships for ST students 23. National Fellowship and Scholarship for Higher Education of ST Students 24. Vocational Training Centres in Tribal Areas 25. Post-matric scholarships for minorities students 26. Merit-cum-means based scholarship for minorities students for professional and technical courses undergraduate and postgraduate 27. Free Coaching & Allied Scheme for Minorities 28. Support for minorities students clearing preliminary examinations conducted by UPSC, SSC, State PSCs, etc. 29. Interest subsidy on education loans for overseas studies for minorities students 30. Maulana Azad National Fellowship for minorities students 31. Vocational Training Centres in Tribal Areas 32. Umbrella Programme for Skill Development of Minorities: I. Seekho aur Kamao – Skill Development Initiatives for minorities ii. Upgrading Skills and Training Development (USTAAD) for minorities iii. Nai Manzil- The Integrated educational and Livelihood initiatives 33. National Scheme for Incentive to Girl Child for Secondary Education (NSIGSE) 36. Prime Minister's Girls' Hostel 34. Assistance to Disabled Persons for purchase of Fitting Devices (ADIP) 35. Deendayal Disabled Rehabilitation Scheme (DDRS) Scholarships for students with disabilities 36. Support to Establishment/ Modernization/ Capacity augmentation of Braille Presses 37. Establishment of Colleges for Deaf 38.

National Program for Persons with Disabilities 39. National Fellowship for Persons with Disabilities (PwD) 40. Pre-and post-matric Scholarship to students with disabilities 41. National Overseas Scholarship for Students with Disabilities 42. Free Coaching for SC and OBC Students 43. Boys and Girls Hostels 44. SIPDA (Schemes for the Implementation of the Persons with Disabilities (Equal Opportunities, Protection of Rights and Full Participation) Act, 1995 45. Saakshar Bharat 46. Vanbandhu Kalyan Yojana - Development of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs) 47. National Service Scheme (NSS) 48. Schemes for Youth development & Education (Nehru Yuva Kendra Sangathan, National Programme for Youth and Adolescent Development, etc.) 49. Kala Sanskriti Vikas Yojana Culture 50. Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana: i. Development of Skills (Umbrella Scheme) ii. Development of Entrepreneurship (Umbrella Scheme) iii. iv. National Skill Development Agency v. Model ITIs/Multi Skill Training Institutes vi. Apprenticeship and Training (Umbrella Scheme) vii. Scheme of Polytechnics 51. Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan 52. Umbrella Programme for Education of SC, ST, OBC and minorities students 53. Umbrella ICDS 54. Umbrella Programme for Education of SC, OBC and vulnerable group students Social Justice & Empowerment 55. Umbrella Programme for Education of ST students 56. Umbrella Programme for Education of minorities students, 57. Pandit Madan Mohan Malaviya National Mission on Teachers and Teaching 58. Teachers Training and Adult Education. (*SDG INDIA INDEX*, n.d.)

IV. CONCLUSION

NEP 2020 is a policy that have potential to change education system of India but policy's effectiveness will depend on its implementation, if NEP will be implemented as expected only then it will be effective otherwise it will have no importance. The data presented above indicates that trends in school and higher education in India are progressive. While improvements have been made in terms of total enrollment, dropout rate, and gender parity index, India lags behind many other nations when compared to other nations. The table below compares India's performance in terms of gender, education, and inequality with that of other nations; it ranks 121st out of 163 in terms of achieving Sustainable Development Goals. On the basis these data it is concluded that India has need to change its education system that will be done through NEP 2020. This paper is also presenting the comparison table of 4th SDG and NEP 2020 that shows initiatives taken under NEP 2020 that will help in achieving the targets of 4th SDG. For boosting India towards achieving 4th SDG India need education policy like NEP 2020.

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